

In The Court of the Neo-U

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Since the days when Kings and Queens protected Peasants, in exchange for loyalty and servitude, titles have defined roles in hierarchy.

Corporate CEOs learned from royalty. They adopted wording, labels and symbols that are “the corporate equivalent of titles, robes, crests, crowns, thrones and even palaces. To think like a royal, savvy leaders manage these tools for optimal impact” [1]. Just as royalty would go amongst the masses (occasionally), business leaders will go amongst the workers (at company picnics). Allowing employees to participate with leaders in different ways is a tool that savvy leaders manage for optimal impact.

Royalty influenced corporations. Corporations influenced universities. Universities adopted corporate operations in the 1980's. For a time, administrators remained administrators and non-administrators remained team members (shared governance remained in place, sort of [2]). When new hierarchy titles did come, they came fast. At my university, administration started referring to itself as Executive Leadership overnight. The word ‘administration’ was struck from all messaging [3]. The newspeak for Administrators was Leaders. Then the coup de grace: The newspeak for Faculty and Staff was Employees.

The new wording and new titles, to drive a new narrative of what a university is, was

riceuniversity 1d ...
Rice University's President's Office, the Rice Recreation Employee Well-Being Team and campus leadership kicked off the inaugural Wellness Wednesdays. The initiative is dedicated to faculty and staff well-being and focuses on a comprehensive approach to health and wellness, featuring many opportunities for employees to participate with university leaders in different ways. bit.ly/3W6PB...

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crystalized in a social media post from my university – shown at left. The telling line: “... opportunities for employees to participate with university leaders ...”

At least the powers that be in the C-Suites are being completely honest and have dropped all pretense that the rest of us are viewed as essential players on a team.

The corporatization of universities was never about a team. It's about leaders and employees. If you're not a leader, you're just another employee.

But leadership is willing to fraternize with employees, who they seem to think are un-well, by offering ‘many opportunities to participate with them in different ways.’

Kiss the ring, share a picnic table, or have your yoga mats close to one another.

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After the Fact

Shortly after I finished the essay above, I received an email with the header below:

From: Rice University <cs@perkspot.com>
Subject: Treat yourself to 3 lbs of wings 🍗
Date: September 19, 2024 at 6:59:50 AM PDT
To:

Seems my university leadership teamed up with PerkSpot – a third-party company that provides coupons from companies they work with. They also track data from those who use the coupons cause, well you know, consumer data is valuable.

The rationale for university leaders teaming with a coupon company is simple: Corporate leadership knows full well that its employees prefer perks to cost of living raises (see for example: <https://www.buzzfeed.com/hannahmarder/incentives-jobs-offered-instead-of-raises>). It's not a stretch to think that PerkSpot gives something back to university leadership in exchange (cause, well you know, consumer data is valuable).

Initially, I felt insulted to be offered coupons from my university leadership. But insult turned to amusement. I found it deliciously ironic that a message proclaiming how much leadership cares for employee health was followed by an email with the subject line of "Treat yourself to 3lbs of wings." After all, what says we care about your health more than 3lbs of chicken wings?

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